

Review of the Impact of Energy Storage on Grid with PV system

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Abstract: This paper aims to comprehensively analyse the critical variables of how photovoltaic systems with battery storage systems influence a community. This study thoroughly analyses the impact of solar energy sources on the local grid. The use of batteries to store electricity in conjunction with photovoltaic systems and their early stages of development have been examined. The contribution of energy storage technologies to extending solar power plants' lifetime, efficiency and energy abundance has been discussed. In addition, methods of using energy storage systems to solve critical problems with renewable energy, such as low capacity, harmonics and inertia reduction, have been demonstrated.

1. Introduction

Integrating renewables into grid resilience systems is complicated by their dependence on climatic and meteorological factors and technological advances in communication and information. In particular, the non-linear and low inertia characteristics can significantly reduce the fluctuation capabilities of the grid and minimise the stability zones. In addition, the unpredictable and intermittent nature of renewable energy sources requires the accessibility and rapid response of flexible authorities. This increases the computational complexity of problem-solving techniques, making implementing strategies even more challenging.

Numerous renewable energy sources also change the behaviour of both transmission and distribution infrastructures. With an emphasis on the operational and structural resilience of power grids, this special issue focuses on these challenges and essential solutions to support grid resilience in reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Government regulations, increasing investment and consumer habits actively encourage the transition to renewable energy. However, high levels of renewable energy penetration can make it challenging to plan and implement strategies to improve the adaptability of the electricity system. Furthermore, resilience has been identified as a need of increasing importance of extreme phenomena and disasters, including disruptions to power generation and distribution that go beyond the stability of the electrical infrastructure.

Renewable energy sources (RES) can effectively mitigate the problems caused by greenhouse gas emissions. However, they have intermittent power generation and specific building specifications. Therefore, grid integration of RES can bring new difficulties regarding power quality, reliability, power infrastructure security and harmonics. These complications caused by the specific nature of renewable energy sources can be reduced by combining them with Battery Storage Systems (BSS).

2. Literature review

Various techniques are used to size BESS from the system specifications.

Different optimisation strategies, known as estimation methods, have been developed for systems that include battery storage and PV. For example, the Markov chain

decision optimises battery sizing optimisation due to its simple structure. In addition, an MCDM used in [2] to optimally schedule energy storage devices for renewable energy sources is unpredictable; many applications recommend using metaheuristic methods. These methods provide more accurate results [3] for complex and non-linear optimisation problems.

Compared to other metaheuristic optimisation methods, the Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) technique is straightforward and easy to use but also has a high convergence rate [4]. Its robustness results from its dependence on the initial point setting being less than that of other techniques. Other metaheuristic algorithms require more factors than the PSO algorithm. It also requires less data storage [5].

Examples of quantitative techniques are linear programming and dynamic programming [6]. Although DP is used in [7], it is challenging to implement in large-scale systems.

As a less complex option, LP optimisation is chosen in [8] and implemented for a remote energy storage system in [9]. However, it has some drawbacks when used in large-scale networks. LP and DP must be adequate tools for complicated processes [10].

For the best sizing of batteries, solar, wind and diesel in a microgrid, the Grasshopper optimisation algorithm is an additional technique [11].

In a combined energy system [13], the Genetic Algorithm (GA) optimises costs and energy storage. The main limitation of GA is the inconclusiveness of its results [8]. In [14], the Bat Algorithm (BA) determines the optimal BESS capacity for a grid-connected low-voltage microgrid.

Grey Wolf Optimisation (GWO) is chosen for optimal BESS sizing and fuel consumption reduction, and the performance of GWO is compared with BA and PSO in [12].

To determine the ideal BESS size and cost reduction, the PSO-based frequency optimisation algorithm for a self-sustaining microgrid is put into practice [15].

The Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm is applied to increase revenue in a hybrid power system to calculate the ideal battery size and operation [16].

However, probabilistic methods work well when there are fewer (typically one) optimised factors [5]. Therefore, these techniques are inappropriate for combining the

improvement of the two factors in the study structure's energy management system.

3. PV grid-connected installation issues

Direct grid integration of solar power sources faces challenges. Designers use grid integration - grid-tie inverters to connect renewable energy sources to the system.

Because renewable energy sources are limited, inverters draw energy from the grid and return energy when more power is produced. The connection and disconnection of renewable energy infrastructure should be completed in 100 milliseconds [2]. In a grid-tied PV system, the primary function of the inverter is to use electrical grid feedback to adjust the magnitude and phase of the PV system's output.

When a current or voltage has a frequency that is an integer multiple of the primary power frequency, it is said to be harmonic. All electrical equipment and generators produce harmonics, and when used in significant quantities, they can cause interference and various power quality problems. However, due to their widespread placement on the grid and low harmonic current output, most grid-connected converters for distributed generation applications are unlikely to cause harmonic problems, even at significant penetration levels.

Voltage source inverters can provide the harmonic support the grid needs, whereas the most popular form of the inverter (current source) cannot. However, they do so at an energy cost and with the same number of harmonic compensators, which are likely less expensive. Both benefit from the reduction in energy losses when using VSDs, and labelling that indicates the type of controller (voltage or current source) would make it easier to purchase current existing target source inverters as required. It should be noted that, unless otherwise configured, PV inverters will disconnect from the grid when there is insufficient sunlight to compensate for switching losses. Therefore, harmonic support would only be provided during daytime hours.

4. PV-made fluctuations in the grid

The different voltage and frequency fluctuation types are grid-induced voltage instability and increase, power factor correction, voltage imbalance and reverse power flow. The impact of the output variability of grid-connected photovoltaic power generation on the electricity grid is primarily seen in the areas of influence on electrical system planning, power quality and impact on electricity grid management and scheduling.

The grid needs adequate reserves to compensate for the variable PV output, which cannot meet the requirements of a stable, continuous and reliable power supply. In addition, the fluctuating PV output will also result in some distribution and transmission equipment.

Reducing PV output fluctuations and setting higher standards for grid operation control are necessary to ensure grid operation reliability and power quality. In addition, variations in PV output have challenges or difficulties to predicts and, thus, planning the power grid.

The grid's voltage will fluctuate when the output fluctuations of the PV system reach a certain level, and it will also affect the grid's frequency. As the PV output decreases, the production of the grid-connected inverter becomes a light load, increasing the current harmonic storage capacity waste, which challenges the rational planning of the grid...

5. Need for battery storage

Recent growth in the use of local generation and sustainable energy sources has increased interest in energy storage devices. They can be installed at different levels, such as the grid, the substation and the small town. However, such equipment costs are falling, making it possible for commercial and industrial customers to use and adopt battery storage. This is made possible by the high price of peak loads and unplanned grid outages.

The economics are sound because battery storage can prevent additional fossil fuel generation at peak times. Peak power is also much more valuable. Pumped hydro generators, typically located in remote areas, require additional infrastructure investment to provide flows and transfer capacity to load centres. Storage also plays the role of fast response, which helps with escalation and overall reliability.

Electrical energy storage can be costly and essential in a thorough system optimisation strategy. However, electricity storage is feasible in some circumstances and should be explored. These include positioning at key nodes where storage can provide the extra capacity to handle peak loads or a place to 'park' excess electricity produced by renewable sources when it's not needed for the momentary demand.

If energy is not stored, it must be used as soon as it is produced. By storing energy, excess production can be saved for peak demand. In the case of renewables, keeping extra energy allows electricity to flow after the sun has gone down or the wind has stopped blowing. As mentioned above, energy storage is filled during periods of high production and low demand periods during periods of reduced production and excessive consumption.

High peak loads threaten the system's stability by overloading distribution and transmission lines. Advanced energy storage systems integrated with PV systems can provide a viable answer to these problems when combined with PV systems. When deployed at the utility and communities level, they can offer a possible solution to the above issues.

The most effective use of any solar panel system is to store the excess energy generated. This can reduce costs, improve grid performance, and reduce fossil fuel emissions. However, the benefits of solar energy storage are based on an electricity infra vulnerable to interruptions and outages caused by everything from wildfires to extreme weather. By shifting power supplies, renewable energy storage protects us from the unexpected.

Battery storage can reduce a property's carbon footprint in areas where electricity is generated from fossil fuels by giving more control over how much solar energy is used. For example, large solar batteries can power any household appliance and help charge electric vehicles. In addition, solar energy storage provides a steady flow of energy during generator outages caused by passing clouds or regular maintenance.

6. Battery storage functionalities in the grid with PV

For the grid with PV system operation, battery storage can be set to at least six functionalities, including peak

shaving, power control, frequency support, target SoC, voltage support and demand response.

6.1. Peak shaving

Peak shaving works by charging the battery when a meter reading falls below a set of configurable thresholds and discharging it when it rises.

Based on the meter readings, separate thresholds can be set for when the system should charge and discharge. Using an interface, the meter must be configured independently and can be an eightsome or an industrial type.

The so-called PI-controller, used by the peak shaving method, gradually changes the power when the meter value changes. This is done to avoid the grid's quality being negatively impacted by sudden changes in electricity—the speed at which the power increases and decreases will depend on these factors. As a result of the current settings, the compensations are relatively slow (range of minute).

6.2. Power control

In this mode, the battery's intended charge/discharge power for a given time is sent to the battery storage system as active and reactive power setpoints (in % of S_{max} or Q_{max}). Applications include reactive power compensation, time of use, demand response and supply.

By assisting in fault clearance, the battery storage system can also increase the short-circuited potential of the distribution line, preventing or reducing transformer overloads and increasing grid security.

6.3. Frequency support

Adding energy storage to the system makes the frequency more stable when using significant amounts of grid-connected PV generation. In addition, this component has a fast power response time and can create a kind of motion for primary frequency control.

An energy storage system control approach that does not change the current flat/smooth control of the battery storage but adds a second response to the frequency according to the basic principles of the traditional control system.

6.4. Target SoC

Reaching The target SoC is to achieve a specific state of charge (SoC) of the power supply at the end of a specified period. Therefore, it is recommended to discharge the battery if the target SoC at the end of a period is lower than the SoC at the beginning. On the other hand, it is necessary to charge the battery if the target SoC at the end of the period is greater than the initial SoC.

The target SoC and the duration are the configuration parameters for this application. After the interval, the service determines the charge/discharge power required to achieve the target SoC.

For the duration of the cycle, this number is recalculated once every minute. The SoC will therefore increase or decrease linearly. The availability of the battery

SoC number is a prerequisite for this service. The charge and discharge power required for the SoC are calculated using charge and discharge mode efficiency factors.

6.5. Voltage support

An energy storage device can help to maintain the grid voltage by injecting or withdrawing both active and reactive power. Integrating a storage system and determining the required energy to reduce node voltages to a safe level is possible.

The main challenge for centralised and distributed concepts is determining the minimum storage capacity to achieve the voltage target. This can be done with numerous storage participation, with storage participation dispread across different grid locations.

6.6. Demand response

In this mode, a power reference is sent to the battery storage system, which includes the capacity required to charge/discharge the battery for a given time. By time-dependent rates, demand response offers customers the chance to significantly influence how the electric grid operates by decreasing or moving their energy consumption during peak hours.

If it's positive, the battery is charged; if it's negative, it is discharged and returned to the grid. Although connected to the grid, its ability to capture and discharge batteries is limited.

7. Benefits of Combining PV system and Energy Storage

Combined PV and battery storage systems offer companies significant cost benefits; open, integrated PV and battery storage systems provide companies robust cost benefits, new revenue streams, increased energy security and resilience, and reduced carbon impact.

Regulating electricity demand, supporting solar energy production and promoting resilience are the key benefits of combined PV and energy storage systems, which are described below.

7.1. Adjusting electricity load

With storage, energy can be produced and consumed simultaneously, which may require grid operators to 'curtail' some generation to prevent overproduction and grid reliability problems. On the other hand, there may be periods of limited solar generation but high electricity demand, such as after sunset or on cloudy days.

Energy storage can be topped up or charged when power consumption is low, generation is high and then used when demand or need is high. In addition, if some of the solar energy generated is stored, it can be used whenever the system operator needs it, even after sunset. In this way, storage acts as solar insurance.

7.2. Securing solar power production

Short-term storage can prevent a solar plant's output from being significantly affected by sudden changes in a generation. For example, the grid can use a small battery to ride out a brief interruption caused by a passing cloud to maintain a stable, reliable, and consistent supply.

7.3. Supplying durability

In a blackout, solar and storage can provide backup power. They can sustain critical infrastructure to maintain essential services such as communications. In addition to microgrids and smaller-scale applications such as portable or battery-powered units, solar and storage can be used.

8. Conclusions

This paper proposes different storage strategy alternatives for grids with PV systems. It is considered that additional energy is needed to address the described problems of grid-connected PV systems and PV-induced fluctuations in the grid.

The functionalities provided by energy storage for the grid with PV systems show that peak shaving, power control, frequency support, target SoC, voltage support and demand response can improve system efficiency. However, it has been shown that more research is needed to achieve a better quality of grid processes with PV installations to benefit from the advantages discussed.

8.1. Journal articles

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